

*And the Prince Turned into a Peasant and Lived
Happily Ever After*

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Breaking the Magic Spell: Radical Theories of Folk and Fairy Tales, by
Jack Zipes. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1979.

For a radical theoretician like Jack Zipes, fairy tales have to be worthwhile; they represent "the collective, active participation of the people," and the people know best. But fairy tales are fantasy, and radical theoreticians usually consider fantasy an escapist diversion from the necessary consideration of things as they are. Darko Suvin, a Marxist critic of science fiction who admires just that one sort of fantasy enough to insist on its political usefulness, has nothing but disdain in *Metamorphoses of Science Fiction* (Yale University Press, 1979), for what he calls "the Great Pumpkin antics" of most fantasy. Fairy tales are filled with Great Pumpkin antics; some of them even describe how Great Pumpkins are turned into great coaches. Even worse, fairy tales originated back when a repressive aristocracy held all power, and even a bourgeois, pseudo-intellectual, would-be capitalist like myself can see that the values they express are feudal, outmoded, and not likely to promote the revolution. A radical theory of fairy tales is bound to be unwieldy, and Zipes does not bring off the impossible acrobatics he attempts in *Breaking the Magic Spell*. But following him as he tries to do so is stimulating and suggests much about fairy tales as children's literature.

Zipes claims that socio-historical forces express themselves in fairy tales in different ways at different points in history. As the collective creation of a precapitalist people, folktales express "their wishes to attain better living conditions." Later, literary fairy tales such as "Beauty and the Beast" show how the superficially bestial aristocracy is morally superior to the "crass, vulgar values of the emerging bourgeoisie," while the witch in "Hansel and Gretel" represents "the entire feudal system or the greed and brutality of

the aristocracy." In our own century, the dragon in Tolkien's *The Hobbit* is "the capitalist exploiter," and folktales, refashioned by the mass media, merely confirm the passive values of a consumer society.

Zipes's attempts to allegorize the evil characters of fairy tales are not convincing. Using the same specious logic, businessmen might see the dragon as the AFL-CIO.; women might see it as men, children as their parents, dopers as the narcs. We all have our dragons.

But having located the specific meanings of fairy tales in history, Zipes can perform the operation basic to his argument: he can separate their distasteful values from their thrust as a *kind* of literature. He can admit that folktales affirm dangerous feudal values but still say that they have "emancipatory potential." He can acknowledge the solipsistic escapism of the fairy tales written in Germany in the early nineteenth century, but he can see it as a socially valuable refusal "to be formed by the powers of domination." And he can insist that those old stories that once had emancipatory potential now merely co-opt our individual imaginations when communicated by mass media.

Zipes doesn't always present these ideas clearly. He rarely discusses individual tales, preferring instead to summarize in abstract jargon the abstract arguments of numerous German leftist theoreticians. He assumes that his analysis of a few German fairy tales allows him to draw general conclusions about the history of all European folktales. He seems to confuse the way in which folktales were created with the values they express, so that any collective creation is assumed—incorrectly—to promote collective values. And he doesn't make clear whether he dislikes the co-opting power of the mass media in general or something specific to mass-media versions of fairy tales. He claims to argue the second of these possibilities but only writes about the first.

With good reason—mass-media culture is popular culture, enjoyed by the mass of the populace. Zipes could not attack the values it promotes without attacking The People. Not surprisingly, his discussion of mass media never mentions demographics—the insidious way in which the communications industry figures out what

most of us want and then gives it to us. He will not admit that there is junk on television, simply because most of us like junk; instead, he insists that “the audiences are the underdogs in the fight against the mass media which expertly exploit their humble daydreams to protect the vested interests of corporate capitalism.” Similarly, he wants to admire the collective humble daydreams of the folk of the Middle Ages, but he has to admit that what those folk collectively probably dreamed of was becoming rich kings with the power to lord it over other humble peasants.

The essential flaw in Zipes’s argument is that he uses the words *wishes* and *hopes* to mean two different things at the same time: not just dreams or daydreams, but also aspirations. Peasants in the Middle Ages did enjoy dreaming about being kings, but only because they knew they would always be peasants. And I suspect it is still true that the people convinced of their continuing powerlessness are those who most enjoy films and stories in which losers win. “Humble daydreams” are just that, ways of imaginatively purging our frustrations about the things we feel humbled by: escapist wish-fulfillment, not utopian aspiration.

But Zipes insists that folktales represent events that might actually happen. For him, even the worst of popular films expresses a utopianism that offers viewers “some small amount of hope for a qualitatively better future.” In turning fairy tales into descriptions of achievable utopias Zipes has a disconcerting effect on them; he really does break their magic spells, by dissipating their magic. Those wonderfully illogical happenings that allow foolish or passive underdogs to triumph over their smarter enemies were not so illogical after all; no, “the magic and miraculous serve to rupture the feudal confines and represent metaphorically the conscious and unconscious desires of the lower classes.” So Zipes saves fairy tales for socialism by denying that they are fantasy.

Bruno Bettelheim does that, too. But according to Zipes, Bettelheim’s rigid Freudian interpretation of the stories foolishly disregards both Zipes’s political prejudices and his revisionist Freudianism, which, unlike the Freudianism of both Bettelheim and Freud, does not confuse adjusting to reality with accepting repressive, bourgeois, capitalist values. Even worse, Bettelheim

believes the old tales in their original versions have a permanent, true meaning, always understood by the human unconscious, and automatically will have a therapeutic effect on children who hear them. But having located the meaning of the tales in the shifting sands of history, Zipes assures us that imposing the feudal values of the old tales on the unconscious minds of contemporary children will be anything but good for them. We must instead choose the *right* tales, the ones “which suggest means by which children can implement their imagination to promote collective action.”

In other words, fairy tales are useful. Zipes and Bettelheim both defend fairy tales, not as good stories, but as stories that are good for people. Both are convinced of the dangers of children’s literature containing values of which they don’t approve. So Zipes’s discussion of Bettelheim offers the instructive spectacle of one angry utilitarian attacking another angry utilitarian; it shows how even the most liberal-minded adults are perfectly willing to limit the freedom of children. Neither Zipes nor Bettelheim has enough respect for children to allow them access to a variety of values, so that they may themselves discover and invent their own world.

As it happens, fairy tales are a good way for children to do that—as Zipes and Bettelheim both unintentionally make clear. Zipes’s radical interpretations appear just as possible as Bettelheim’s Freudian ones, or, for that matter, as Madame de Beaumont’s aristocratic ones or as contemporary anti-sexist ones. But that the tales support such wildly different interpretations suggests that the interpretations are just variants, other ways of telling stories whose main characteristic is their openness to being told in different ways, with different meanings. What really matters about fairy tales is not their meanings, for we all are capable of devising different ones. What matters is that fairy tales allow us to do so, that they offer us a gift of interpretative freedom, a way to explore and discover ourselves and our own stories. Wise children respect and enjoy that gift; so should wise critics.